

Experimental investigation of alternative plasma gases for enhanced radiation in microwave plasma torches

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Microwave plasma offers several advantages across various industrial applications. It enables highly efficient and targeted energy transfer to materials, resulting in lower energy consumption compared to conventional high temperature processes such as liquid and gaseous burners. Conventional plasma torches are normally operated with air or nitrogen, sadly these gases suffer from limited radiative emission at high temperatures. That's why this study investigates potential different plasma gases like water vapor and carbon dioxide. The focus is set on CO₂ that can be separated from different industrial processes and afterwards gets heated as a plasma gas. Following it can be used as a volumetric heat source for thermal processes. The high purity of CO₂ allows the further use in carbon capture and storage (CCS) pathways.

Motivation

- There are many ways to achieve the electrification of high temperature processes
- Main Focus on Microwaves and furthermore Microwave Plasma
- Because conventional resistive heating is limited, plasma torches can replace burners relatively easy -> process changes are expected to be minimal
- Microwave generators are available up to 100 kW for 915 MHz and 30 kW for 2.45 GHz (Normally water cooled, when exceeding 1 kW of microwave power)
- The average hot gas temperature of plasma torches can be approximated by Formula 1

Figure 1: Schematic structure of electrification

$$T_{Gas,hot} = \frac{P_{MW}}{\dot{V}_{Gas} \cdot c_{Gas}} + T_{Gas,cold}$$

Formula 1: Approximation for hot gas temperature in plasma torches
(T_{Gas} - Gas Temperature (cold/hot), P_{MW} - Microwave Power, \dot{V} - Flow Rate Gas, c_{Gas} - specific heat capacity)

Plasma Torch

Figure 2: Scheme of the plasma torch and its components

CO₂ Plasma - Experiments

Figure 3: Different types of plasma torch nozzles (quartz glass tubes), that result in different plasma shapes

Microwave plasma torch parameters

- 2.45 GHz MW Plasma under atmospheric conditions
- Minimum/Maximum Power: 1 kW / 10 kW
- Operating Gases: O₂, N₂, Air, H₂, CO₂, Ar, Water Vapor, NH₃, CO

Using carbon dioxide as a plasma gas

- Normally used gases: air, nitrogen -> low radiative emissions
 - Advantage of carbon dioxide: possible high radiative emissions at high temperatures
- With more radiative emissions the substitution of fossil fuels (oil, natural gas) is easier, because those already have high radiative emissions in the field of high temperature processes
- Carbon dioxide is the product of many industrial processes
 - Usage as plasma gas afterwards -> gets heated
 - Heated gas as volumetric heat source in thermal processes
 - Still at high purity after cooling down
 - Carbon Capture and Storage (CCUS)

		Temperature for 44 % Ionization [°C]						Temperature for 85 % Ionization [°C]										
		40	60	80	100	120	140	40	60	80	100	120	140					
Power [kW]	1	1915	1152					1133										
	2	4203	2678	1915	1457	1152		2317	1527	1133								
	3	6491	4203	3059	2372	1915	1588	3501	2317	1725	1370	1133						
	4		5728	4203	3288	2678	2242	4686	3107	2317	1843	1527	1302					
	5			7254	5347	4203	3440	2895	5870	3896	2909	2317	1922	1640				
	6				6491	5118	4203	3549	7054	4686	3501	2791	2317	1979				
	7					7635	6033	4966	4203		5475	4094	3264	2712	2317			
	8						6948	5728	4857			6265	4686	3738	3107	2655		
	9							7864	6491	5510				7054	5278	4212	3501	2994
	10								7254	6164					7844	5870	4686	3896

Figure 4: Approximation of the hot gas temperatures in plasma according to Formula 1 for different grades of ionization

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